

Supplemental Table 1. Names purpose and sequences of primers used in this study.

Name	Sequence 5'→3'	Experiment	
GenWalkAdaptator1	GTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGCACGCGT GGTCGACGGCCCCGGGCTGGT	Transposon Display	
GenWalkAdaptator2	(PHOS) ACCAGCCC (AMINO)		
AP1	GTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGC		
Copia78 3'LTR	AACACTTAAACACTTTCTCCA		
284 COPIA78-4219F_RT	CCACAAGAGGAACCAACGAA	qPCR	
285 COPIA78-4219R_RT	TTCGATCATGGAAGACCGG		
ONSEN probe	(FAM) AAG TCG GCA ATA GCT TTG GCG AAG A (BHQ1)		
ACT2_QT_F	TGCCAATCTACGAGGGTTTC		
ACT2_QT_R	TTACAATTTCCCGCTCTGCT		
ACT2_QT_probe	(JOE) TCCGTCTTGACCTTGCTGGACG (BHQ-1)		
OnsenFull_F	AAGTGGTATCAGAGCTTGAAGATCC		
OnsenFull_R	CAACACCCCCTCTTAAACTTGATTTTGC		
M13F	CGCCAGGGTTTTCCCAGTCACGAC	Cloning and sequencing	
M13R	TCACACAGGAAACAGCTATGAC		
houba_F2	ATCCTGGGAAGAACAACCATTA	PCR on circular rice TE and the chloroplast control	
houba_R2	GAGTTCGAGTACCTTAGCCATGGT		
Chloroplast cyc F	ACAACCACTGATGAAGGATT		
Chloroplast cyc R	AGAAAGAAAAGCAACGACTG		
Prove TED 2_20 R	ACCTAGCTCTGAGTGATGAA	# 1	Genotyping of novel ONSEN insertions
Prove TED4_27 F	TGGATATACACATTGGTTGCA	# 2	
Prove TED 2_19 F	GGAGAAAGCTGAAAACCTGG	# 3	
Prove TED4_30_rev	CTAGGTTGGTGACTGATGAG	# 4	
Prove TED 2_17 F	AAGAATGGGAGCAGCATTAA	# 5	
Prove3_2R	GCAGTACTATAACCGGGACT	# 6	
prove TED3_1 Fw	GAACCTTCCGTTGTTACCGG	# 7	
Prove TED3 F	ATGAGACAGGGAGCTTATCT	# 8	
Prove TED1 R	GGTGTGAACCGAACCTAAAT	# 9	
Prove TED 4_25 F	AAACACCAGAAATCTTTCGC	# 10	
tt6 fw	CACAGACCACAAGCATTTTT	TT6	gene
tt6 rev	TGTCGATTTTCTTGGTGCTA		

Fig. S1. Increase in *ONSEN* copy numbers in S1 pools of heat-stressed and Z-treated *nrpb2-3* plants. *ONSEN* copy number measured by qPCR in pooled seedlings of the S1-generation of heat stressed and zebularine-treated (10 μ M) WT (light grey bars) and *nrpb2-3* plants (dark grey bars) that were grown under control conditions on soil relative to a control stressed WT-plant (black bar) (mean \pm s.e.m., $n=3$ technical repetitions, all values relative to *ACTIN2*).

Fig. S1.

Fig. S2. Detection of eccDNAs originating from *ONSEN* loci following heat stress and chemical treatments in *Arabidopsis*. Abundance of reads from the mobilome-seq libraries of WT *Arabidopsis* plants mapping at TE-annotated loci from seedlings after: **a** growth under long day conditions (LD), **b** CS plus treatment with A (5 μ g/ml) and Z (40 μ M) (A&Z), **c** HS and **d** HS plus treatment with A&Z. Each dot represents the normalized coverage per million mapped reads per all TE-containing 100bp windows obtained after aligning the sequenced reads on the five chromosomes (black and grey circles). Red dots indicate the position of 100bp windows corresponding to *ONSEN* loci.

Fig. S2.

Fig. S3. Increase in *ONSEN* copy numbers in S1 pools of heat-stressed and A&Z-treated WT plants. Parental plants were heat stressed and treated in independent experiments (characters a-c) with a combination of A (5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and Z (40 μM). Pools with clearly increased *ONSEN*-copy numbers (>10) are marked in red. *ONSEN*-copy number measured by qPCR (mean \pm s.e.m., n=3 technical repetitions, values relative to *ACTIN2*).

Fig. S3.

Fig. S4. Summary of confirmed novel *ONSEN* insertions in hc-line 3. **a** Overview of insertion sites shown in **(b)** (red bar) and the location of the *ONSEN* insertion in the *TT6*-gene depicted in Fig. 4 (blue bar) **b** Close-up of regions with new *ONSEN* insertions (red bar) in the S2 generation of a selected heat stressed and A (5 μ g/ml) and Z (40 μ M) treated WT plant (hc-line 3). Orientation of novel *ONSEN* insertions is indicated with red arrows. **c** A scheme to exemplify the annotation of sequences that lead to the identification of novel *ONSEN* insertion sites depicted in **(b)** shown for insertion # 9. Colors correspond to the pGEM-T vector (light blue) used for cloning, the *ONSEN*- 3'LTR (red), the Copia 78 TE 3'LTR primer (dark green) that was used for the preceding TE-Display PCR and the genomic region (turquoise) flanking the 3'LTR of the new *ONSEN* insertion. **d** Summary of coordinates (base 5' of insertion) of new *ONSEN* insertions shown in **(a)** and **(b)**. Numbering corresponds to **(b)**. Sequences of primers used to confirm new *ONSEN* insertions are given with the numbering corresponding to **(b)** in Additional file 1: Table S1.

Fig. S4.

Fig. S5. Stress-induced activation of *ONSEN* in the S3 generation after initial HS-treatment. *ONSEN* copy number measured by qPCR directly after HS and HS plus treatments with α -amanitin (A, 5 μ g/ml) and zebularine (Z, 40 μ M) in seedlings of the WT, the control line a and the hc-lines 3 and 4. *ONSEN* copy number is shown relative to the WT HS (mean \pm s.e.m., $n=3$ biological repetitions, all values relative to *ACTIN2*).

Fig. S5.

